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BLACK INK, WHITE DREAM

A Short Story

Light in the future... Dispelling the cries... The echo of hardship, concealed yet bringing life to the dead. On the towering ramparts of dreams, one can conquer the shadows and shake off the chains of poverty and ignorance.

I've witnessed this, during times when my mind takes flight. I hold a long vehicle spewing its black ink, revealing a radiant light. Light that takes me wherever I desire, and the oppressive, iron bars with their burdens have no power here, thus they are deflected.

"Good morning Dr. Mar, there are papers from CHED that you need to read and if you like, please sign the last page," Manuel, his secretary, greets him upon entering their office, carrying a glass of coffee and a bread roll he bought from Mang Kanoy.

"Well, this is good for the child we'll choose to send; he'll just use his writing skills, a scholarship will be his immediately," he replies to his secretary after dipping the still warm bread roll into his favorite coffee.

When he was just starting his career as a teacher, he met Mang Kanoy at the side street of the university where he worked. The 21-year-old Mar was starving and looking for something to eat. Just then, Mang Kanoy offered him a warm bread roll for two pesos, which filled his stomach. Mang Kanoy's image became like a father to Mar since he was abandoned by his own father when he was just a child.

Manuel inquires, "Sir, do you have anyone in mind to join?"

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"Call Mam Lourdes, tell her to come here, I'll talk to her."

"Yes, sir," he replies.

"By the way, sir, I already talked to the priest of Hagonoy about blessing your new four-story house; he said he can bless it on Saturday, at exactly ten o'clock, he'll be going to your place."

"Oh, is that so, okay, I'll tell Mama to prepare," Mar says.

Mar has long dreamed of that house for his beloved mother. After graduating with a degree in Education, he immediately worked hard to pass the LET and get his license. Fate was kind to him because he not only passed the exam, which he had always dreamed of, but he was also named among the Top 5 for that year. Opportunities opened up on all sides, until he became Dean. His mother and those who helped him were the pillars of his strength to reach his goals. He wanted to be successful because he wanted to give back to the people who helped him from the beginning; and also, he wanted to buy his mother her own home.

"Sir, Mam Lourdes is here."

"Good day Mam, I just wanted to tell you something."

"What is it, Doc?" Lourdes asks nervously.

"Why do you seem nervous, Mam?"

"It's just a little bit, Doc; this is the first time you called me to your office."

"It's good news, Mam, because you know, you have a student who is good at writing, the one we submitted to the Inter-University competition?"

"Yes, Doc, I have him now," Lourdes replies.

"There's a writing competition that CHED will hold. You know, the prize is big, a scholarship, it covers all allowances and dorm."

"We'll have that child join, train him well."

"Yes, Doc, I'll take care of it, thank you."

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It was almost seven o'clock when Mar decided to go home. Upon leaving the university, he decided to call his mother to join him for dinner. As fast as the clock moved, he arrived at his mother's house. The two immediately changed and, using his new blue car, they went to their favorite restaurant in Pasay. Upon arriving, they were immediately attended to by more than four staff at the restaurant. They were given a good spot and offered their menu. Mar's mother loves tilapia, so that's what she ordered. That evening ended happily. Mar was happy because he knew he had made the only woman in his life happy.

The next day, the sun was shining brightly, the mother and son hurriedly got ready to go to the blessing of the four-story mansion Mar had built in Hagonoy, Bulacan. Using his other red car, they stopped by his siblings' house and all went to the mansion together. After the blessing, Mar answered a call from his friend Anna. He agreed to her invitation to participate in a community service project. The clock struck five in the morning. Although still sleepy, Mar forced himself to get out of bed and off of his comfortable mattress.

A certain organization conducted weekly free tutoring and feeding programs for disadvantaged children, and his friend Anna persuaded him to experience this kind of activity for the first time. At seven o'clock in the morning, the group of more than thirty people met at their agreed meeting place. They were all headed to the place where they would volunteer to teach and feed the children. The asphalt road they walked on earlier turned muddy as they entered the stronghold of Marilao in Bulacan – the name of the community they were going to. The mud they were walking on was black, accompanied by unpleasant smells and sights. Despite the modernization and towering buildings in the large province, there were still such places hidden. It seemed they were entering not just a community, but a huge garbage dump. His white shoes were gradually turning black from the soft soil they were walking on. Every house they passed was clearly made of flimsy materials and was very small. You could see the poverty of each resident living there. Perhaps this was the face of poverty.

The children peeking out of the doors and windows smiled broadly, as if they were happy to see them pass by. Although the children were very dirty, their greetings reached his heart.

“Hello, teacher!” “Hi!” “Hello!” They greeted them happily, accompanied by waves.

“Hello too!” He happily returned their greetings.

He was slightly surprised when a little child suddenly held his hand and walked with them. He didn't intend to let go of him, but he was even happy because the child chose him to walk with. As their hands touched, he felt as if the child was thirsty for care. The child also seemed happy to see him, as if he had only seen and held a person for the first time.

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The child was a boy, and he guessed he was only eight years old. Like the children he had first seen, he was also dirty. His shirt and shorts were tattered. His nails were black, and his feet, which were bare, were even blacker. He didn't care about the very muddy road and seemed used to walking there.

"Why don't you have slippers?" He couldn't help but ask the child holding his hand.

"I don't have slippers," the child replied.

"Are you joining the ones we're going to teach?" He asked the child again.

"Yes!" The child answered happily and full of energy.

"Because after we learn, there's free food. So I'm joining."

"Why haven't you bathed yet? Because you look like you're going to school, so you should clean your body first before going in."

"We don't have water." He didn't respond. "We don't have food either. Well, we do, just scraps," sadness crept into the dirty face of the little boy.

"Oh, I see." Dr. Mar continued walking sadly with tears in his eyes.

The child pointed to an old man sitting in a corner of his backyard. The old man was busy digging through a large sack that he thought contained a mixture of leftover food. He was picking at a chicken bone as if he was removing the clinging rice. He did not show his mixed surprise and wonder at what he saw.

When they reached the place that served as a large classroom for the children, the child let go of him. He also lined up with the children whom he thought they would be teaching that morning.

They were busy coloring drawings on each of their papers when suddenly one of his students, Vince, started to tell a story.

"My father left us." He began.

He was slightly surprised, but listened intently to the child's story.

"Why did he leave you?" He asked.

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"Because he has another wife now."

"Who takes care of you and your siblings?" He learned from this that they were three siblings.

"My mother, after my father left us, we became poor."

Mar didn't know what his reaction would be to the child's story. At his young age, he had already experienced a lot in life.

"You know, like your clothes, that's also my dream. I want to be a successful teacher. I want to lift my mother out of poverty. I want to buy her a four-story mansion. I want to buy her two cars, one blue and the other red. I want to treat my mother at an expensive restaurant because she loves tilapia." Dr. Mar was overwhelmed with a range of emotions. His mind was clouded, and his whole being was filled with sorrow. With the strong wind and the white color of the overcast clouds, he held the child's hand tightly. However, for some inexplicable reason, a familiar cry rang in his ear. "Nak! 'Nak! We have dinner, 'Nak! Where are you, 'Nak? I have tilapia, just scraps, but we have meat to eat. 'Nak!" Tere's voice, mixed with joy. Despite his awakening, the overwhelming fatigue and sleepiness prevented the young man who dreamt with the four corners of white paper from waking up; even with his mother's strong voice.

It was already one o'clock in the morning, so when Tere saw her son, she just let him sleep. As she was tidying up the scattered papers on the small kitchenette, she noticed the words stuck on the wall.

"I want to be the Dean of one of the famous universities in Manila. A four-story mansion and two expensive cars (blue and red). I want to take my mother to a restaurant that serves delicious tilapia dishes. I want to follow in the footsteps of the teacher who taught me and gave us food when I was eight years old... he was so good."

"This will come true when I win... a scholarship to study, for my mother!" Tears and sobs flowed at that moment. Tere knew that these words were the mainstay of Marvince's dreams, dreams he put on paper with black ink from his pen. Dreams that she knew were difficult to achieve, but because of his pen and imagination, he seemed to fully savor and experience them realistically. Every letter and word that Marvince formed in his mind was a representation of his strong belief in the power of the pen, that one day, just like his writing, which reflected his dreams, he would also have them in real life. But for now, they remain a song in his ears, the psalm of his pen swaying in the white notebook, the beauty of his dreams.

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